

TEACHING MANUFACTURING SYSTEMS CONCEPTS USING GAME-BASED LEARNING

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Abstract

Purpose – The paper presents a game-based simulation experiment for teaching concepts such as manufacturing systems to industrial engineering students. The entire approach was agile-based and used Scrum as a methodology to conduct students' activities.

Methodology/approach - The methodology proposed in the paper revolves around the concept of using Serious Games (SG) as an educational tool to study manufacturing systems. First, a SG definition model is presented. Second, the Lego-based simulation activity for students is described according to Scrum principles.

Findings – Given the complexity of manufacturing systems, students faced many decision-making challenges that made them understand the importance of their decisions in the outcome. However, the research showed that the simulation game offered a playful learning experience for the students enrolled in the course and we suggest that it can also be replicated in other domains.

Research limitations/implications – lack of collaboration with industries in developing Serious Games for engineering students to get a more hands-on approach when learning engineering concepts.

Practical implications – Due to the increased environmental unpredictability, many of the learning activities must also be carried out online. Game-based learning and Scrum offer such flexibility for students wanting to maintain part of their educational activities online.

Originality/value – Propose a practical exercise using Lego-based software to introduce students to the development of a manufacturing system and to give a closer look at how manufacturing concepts apply in real life.

Key words: manufacturing systems, Scrum, Serious Games

Introduction

This article presents the author's work to develop a gamification framework for conducting training activities for students enrolled in Economic Engineering in Electric, Electronic, and Energetic field, Faculty of Management in Production and Transportation, Politehnica University of Timisoara. Simulation games can be very effective in understanding manufacturing concepts and supporting the teaching process for engineering students.

Product development concepts such as Agile and Scrum methodology are also considered. Agile development concepts not only support the way students learn and work, but also encourage problem solving and teamwork skills. The course activities were guided in an Agile manner, offering students more autonomy and space to receive constant feedback on their work.

The Computer Assisted Manufacturing course is being taught during the second semester of the fourth year of the undergraduate Economic Engineering program in the Electric, Electronic, and Energetic field. The syllabus of this course approaches topics like Manufacturing Systems, Manufacturing Planning, Models and Modeling in Manufacturing, Artificial Intelligence in Manufacturing, Agile manufacturing, Optimization using Machine Learning/Artificial Intelligence Canvas and Flexible Manufacturing Systems. When learning and analyzing manufacturing systems, students are usually limited in learning the theoretical aspects of these concepts, as most industrial engineering courses are (Yiming, 2021). Project-based learning or PBL is considered a more suitable approach for industrial engineering

courses, as stated in (Gani, 2019), but researchers raised several concerns also regarding PBL (Yiming, 2021).

As Yiming (2021) considers, serious games (SG) for higher education have been shown to have a positive impact on the presentation of complex concepts to students enrolled in engineering programs. Serious games, also known as Edutainment or Game-Based Learning, are used to teach specific concepts through gamified exercises and simulations (Yiming, 2021); (Laamarti, Eid and El Saddik, 2014). SGs are attractive for young people and have a low risk of failure, since students practice in a virtual environment and for short periods of time. Many researchers have already developed models and frameworks to analyze the opportunities and limitations of educational games, highlighting the methods in which these games can be structured and used in a way that supports effective learning (Carvalo et al., 2015). Among the perspectives of defining the concept of SG in the research field, a common opinion is that SGs are games with several other purposes in addition to providing entertainment or fun for the user (Laamarti, Eid and El Saddik, 2014). In Figure 1, the author presents the concept of SGs as a system based on three interconnected pillars, Learning & Teaching, Gaming and Simulation, centered on the learner, and clearly showing the fact that training simulation, simulation games and Edutainment are not interchangeable concepts. The Learning&Teaching component addresses, on the one hand, the point of view of the learners and on the other hand, the point of view of the instructor.

Figure 1. Serious games definition model

Based on the SG's definition model from Figure 1, in the present paper the following research questions are addressed:

RQ1: What kinds of skills are students supposed to develop when using gamification in their learning activity?

RQ2: Can agile methodologies such as Scrum, improve efficiency and communication in teams rather than when using traditional project management techniques?

RQ3: How should a serious game be designed to efficiently give engineering students a proper mix between learning and fun?

Game-like activities in Agile Engineering Education

We can approach the concept of Agile by considering it as a philosophy that supports flexibility, adaptability, and innovation. Over the past few years, agile has shown its significant support in many other areas in addition to software development, where it has its roots (Buciuman, 2020). Agile methodologies are also known as flexible product development. Unlike traditional project management techniques focused on following the initial plan, agile or flexible methods use several techniques that allow for a low cost of change (Buciuman, Izvercianu and Seran, 2012). For education, this flexibility can be related to the teacher's ability to change his learning techniques and adapt the approach to meet the diverse needs and abilities of students (Chun, 2004).

For students studying manufacturing and production systems, it is very common to face certain issues in understanding concepts such as design or modelling when using traditional lectures and theoretical explanations (Lugaresi, Frigerio and Matta, 2020).

Gani (2019) summarizes some critical issues that need to be addressed in Engineering Education:

- Technical courses are usually not related to industry topics;
- Students lack practical experience, teamwork experience, and communication skills;
- Teaching and learning methodologies need to be more student oriented;
- Students lack knowledge on the social, legal, and environmental impact of modern engineering technologies.

Many of the activities in the Computer-Assisted Manufacturing course are project-based and can be approached using agile practices. These project activities can be designed as serious games that can provide students with practical application and problem solving skills. Stier (2003) considers that laboratory projects or other practices that offer students hands-on experiences of industry situations can also be of great value to students studying manufacturing concepts.

According to Yiming (2021), serious games have already been applied for production planning in industrial engineering. As benefits of using SG for engineering students, Yiming (2021) highlights:

- practicing the theoretical concepts in a simulated, and safe environment;
- developing skills such as teamwork, leadership, and communication;
- the opportunity to clearly see the impact of their decisions on the outcome.

Using Lego for educational purposes is presented in (Hussain, Lindh and Shukur, 2006) and is based on the belief that students with a technical background that perform better in mathematics tend to be more engaged and successful when learning with Lego training. Yiming (2021) lists several engineering subjects where Lego Mindstorms has been increasingly used as an educational tool, but also states that there are not many approaches of using Lego for manufacturing systems courses.

Methodology

This paper describes a teaching approach developed during the Computer-Assisted Manufacturing course. Students enrolled in the course are asked to use Lego Studio Designer software to design a production system based on the specifications provided by the teacher. As a prerequisite, students should have the appropriate skills to approach practical engineering problems, although most of the courses they take during the four years at the university are standalone courses. For this reason, it was important to offer a more flexible approach that could provide students with the opportunity to nurture teamwork and problem-solving skills and face production issues in a safe and controlled environment.

The manufacturing project was mainly student driven. Students carried out their activities iteratively following the principles of agile Scrum methodology. The project goal was to design a production system in a plant layout with all the features involved in the process. During the development phase, students were asked to find the best configuration of features in terms of quality, meeting the definition of done inflicted by the Scrum methodology. The aim was to teach students the process planning using Lego blocks in a virtual environment.

As in any other type of project, a Scrum project starts by defining the objectives and features of a new product. The resulting list of features is called Product Backlog. Development is iterative and allows for constant inclusion of feedback from one iteration to another. These iterations are called Sprints (Buciuman, 2020). The Scrum framework consists of (Buciuman, Izvercianu and Seran, 2012), (Pejcinovic, Wong and Bass, 2019):

- **A set of roles:** Scrum Master, Product Owner, Team Member;
- **Four types of meetings:** Sprint Planning, Daily Stand-Up, Sprint Review, Sprint Retrospective;
- **Artifacts:** Product Backlog, Sprint Backlog;
- **Commitments:** refers to the need of the Scrum Team to support each other and to pursue a common goal;

Figure 2 illustrates the Scrum framework in practice with all the specific elements listed above. A more detailed explanation of all Scrum features and artefacts can be found in (Schwaber and Sutherland, 2020).

Figure 2. Scrum framework

The person in charge with creating and prioritising the backlog is called the Product Owner. The Development Team represents another category of roles in Scrum. At the beginning of every sprint, Scrum Teams will create a Sprint Backlog. The Sprint Backlog is a list of features that the team needs to complete during a Sprint. Teams are completely in charge of the Sprint Backlog. As stated in (Buciuman, 2020), the Scrum framework can be used as an effective tool for conducting educational activities.

The first phase of the project began with the presentation of the features of the future product. The presentation was made by the teacher, who in this case takes over the role of the Product Owner. The project the students from the 4th year were supposed to approach consisted of the construction of a manufacturing unit. The whole project was Lego-based and was developed using Lego Studio 2.0.

Students were divided into Scrum teams of five people each. To have a clear overview of Scrum artefacts, every team used a Kanban board. For every team, one of the students took the role of the Scrum Master and she was in charge of keeping the Kanban board up to date and to ensure that all Scrum-specific meetings are documented, and that work is properly assigned from one Sprint to another. The Kanban board consists of a set of columns labelled To-do, In Progress and Done. Each User Story from the Sprint Backlog is assigned to one team member and is placed in the To-Do column. After the work is completed, the User Story is moved to the Done column. At any given time, every team member is aware of the status of every feature in the Sprint Backlog. In Figure 3 is an example of a Kanban board layout developed using Miro.

There were situations where students did not attend any of the Daily Meetings, but this was highlighted by the fact that they did not complete the activities they assumed they would do during the Sprint. The topic was discussed during the Sprint Retrospective Meeting. During the Retrospective Meeting, they managed the situation by themselves, and this was a great opportunity to provide students with more control over their learning process. The teacher also provided feedback to each Scrum team, regarding the quality of the completed User Stories, the quality of the Kanban board, and on how the team worked during the Sprint.

Students had seven weeks to complete the project. Each Sprint lasted one week. The first couple of Sprints were the most challenging, because students did not yet have enough experience to effectively estimate the work they can do during a Sprint. This is a process that self-regulates as the Sprints progress, with students learning to appreciate the work that the team can complete in a Sprint more efficiently and properly. At the end of every Sprint, students delivered an increment of the manufacturing process they had to design. The increment consisted of basic elements of a production system, such as conveyors or robotic cells Lego based, which in the end materialized as a production sequence. Figure 4

presents a robotic process and workspace, and Figure 5 shows a robotic assembly cell, all representing increments from different Sprints.

Figure 3. Example of a Miro Kanban board

Figure 4. Robotic process and workspace in Lego Studio 2.0

Figure 5. Robotic assembly line in Lego Studio 2.0

Working in short time intervals, students received rapid feedback on their work and became more aware of the impact that every member of the team has on the outcome. Some of them missed several Daily Meetings and this led to communication issues within the team, but which could be managed during the

Sprint Retrospective Meetings. The students had the opportunity to reflect on how they performed both as a team and individually.

Discussion and Conclusions

The first objective of the paper was to identify the skills students can develop using game-like activities when studying engineering concepts. Following the teacher's observations and the feedback received from students, using Lego as a main tool for understanding manufacturing concepts, it was easier for students previously designing other Lego projects and they tended to be more engaged. The general attitude was positive. By working in Sprints, problem solving skills and improvement in decision-making could be quantified by measuring specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as #Team effort, % Flexibility, or % On-time Delivery. The trend for these KPIs showed better results from one Sprint to another.

Being a transparent process, Scrum facilitated a clear overview of the process and on the activity that all students performed during a Sprint, thus motivating students to be aware of their tasks.

Referring to the second research question, we saw that the agile teaching approach involved a lot of adaptability and allowed both students and teachers to be more committed and to embrace change. Communication with other team members and with the teacher Product Owner was easy-going because of the frequent meetings Scrum implies. It should be mentioned that some of the students worked for the first time in real teams and were comfortable talking about their approaches during the Sprints and about criticizing or, in contrast, appreciating the work of other team members.

There are many success factors that the literature has drawn for designing and developing serious games (Laamarti, Eid and El Saddik, 2014). It is important to mention that educational games have a higher chance of being accepted by teachers if they follow the curriculum and fall within the time frame. The balance between the fun and educational part of a serious game might be subjective. It is important that the game keeps its entertaining part but also fulfills its educational objective, and probably the serious part tends to take over, but we must not forget that the educational purpose can be reached right through the fun component itself. The experience of using Lego to teach manufacturing systems brought new learning experiences for both students and teachers. Considering that the activities were carried out using Scrum, the game-like activities that the students carried out implied a lot of decision making, adaptability, and teamwork spirit. When evaluating this assignment, students stated that they enjoyed integrating gaming into their engineering education and that this made the concepts learned seem more tangible and more accessible. Some of them mentioned that at first, they felt overwhelmed because they did not have much time to learn how to use Lego Studio before the first Sprint and this made them feel anxious at first.

For future experiences in addressing the field of manufacturing systems using serious games, several elements will be considered to improve the way in which the productivity and sustainability of the manufacturing systems students develop are measured.

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